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WORKPLACE ENVIRONMENT: CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Management's new challenge is to create a work environment that attracts, keeps, and motivates its workforce. This responsibility lies with managers and supervisors at all levels of the organization. Businesses must step outside their traditional roles and comfort zones to look at new ways of working. They have to create a work environment where people enjoy what they do, feel like they have a purpose, have pride in what they do, and can reach their potential. The present study has attempted to light on the importance of maintaining a good and harmonious workplace environment. It further explains the Great Place to Work Model developed by Robert Levering and Amy Lyman and outlines ways to create a positive workplace environment.

Keywords-work environment, flexible workplace, trust, pride, camaraderie

1. INTRODUCTION

Ninety - five percent of my assets drive out the front gate every evening. It's my job to bring them back.

— JIM GOODNIGHT, CEO AND FOUNDER OF SAS

What makes a great workplace? It's not what you do. It's how you do it. If you are a leader, you must communicate, make decisions, and interact with people, just as leaders in all companies do. A great workplace is one where people trust the people they work for, take pride in what they do, and enjoy the people they work with.

For instance, TD Industries in Dallas, Tex., has a unique way of making its employees feel valued and involved. One wall in the company has the photographs of all employees who have been with the company for more than five years. Maybe that's why TD Industries was listed in 2011 by Fortune magazine as one of the Top 100 Best Companies.

A good and harmonious working environment is one where all workers are treated with dignity and respect, and where no worker is subjected to harassment by conduct that is related to religious belief or political opinion. Again the same principles will apply with regard to the promotion of a good and harmonious working environment on grounds of race, gender, disability, sexual orientation and age. According to Max Messmer, Chairman and CEO, Robert Half International. "For a growing number of workers, corporate culture is the key determinant in their choice to stay with an organization long term." Regardless of whether it is a business problem or a people problem, culture is a by - product of resolving it successfully. When cost cuts are required, trust is built when you engage people in finding places to save money, share the burden with employees, and use layoffs as a last resort.

2. Objective of the Study

The objective of the present study is to highlight the importance of maintaining a good and harmonious workplace environment. It further explains the Great Place to Work Model developed by Robert Levering and Amy Lyman and outlines ways to create a positive workplace environment.

3. WHAT IS A GREAT WORKPLACE?

"A great place to work is one in which you trust the people you work for, have pride in what you do, and enjoy the people you work with."

— Robert Levering, Co-Founder, Great Place to Work Institute

Researchers, business leaders, media analysts and the public rely on Great Place to Work metrics to establish the definitive standard of what a great workplace is. Great Place to Work's annual research is based on data from more than 10 million employees in 45 countries representing over 5,500 organizations of varying sizes, industries and structures.

Employees believe they work for great organizations when they consistently:

- **TRUST** the people they work for;
- Have **PRIDE** in what they do; and
- **ENJOY** the people they work with.

This fundamental model, confirmed by Great Place to Work through over 25 years worth of analysis of employees' own opinions, is universal and consistent year-over-year, country-to-country, and applies to companies in all industries, non-profits, education and government organizations with wildly diverse employee demographics.

4. BENEFITS OF A GOOD WORKING ENVIRONMENT

Consider, the costs to a business if two employees get into an unproductive exchange, and then return to their work stations or offices. They aren't focused on the task at hand; instead, they are still thinking about the frustrating interaction they just had with their colleague.

Or consider the implication if a team leader fails to address clear roles or goals. The team lurches along, marginally productive but wholly ineffective. Just as any athlete requires the right training and equipment to perform at the highest level, workers require suitable conditions at the office in order to keep performing efficiently.

"A healthy organization creates healthy outcomes for its people – improved health and well-being, and for the organization – reduced costs and improved performance."

-The Graham Lowe Group Inc.

Providing a healthy working environment is not only beneficial for the workers, but increases the efficiency and productivity of the company as a whole. By optimising the sound environment for communication and concentration in your office premises, you're also optimising the company's profitability and improving the company's popularity as a workplace, which in turn can help you attract highly qualified employees.

Research shows that healthy people working in a healthy environment are the key to business success. That's because a healthy workplace improves productivity and reduces employers' costs.

A healthy workplace will:

- Improve employee health outcomes
- Make it easier to attract and retain qualified employees- In environments where trust is present and nurtured, people show up for years. Turnover is lower, which increases efficiency and reduces recruiting and hiring costs.
- Lower absenteeism - The lost productivity that goes along with actual work time lost due to personal reasons is a major business cost. A sound work environment reduces absenteeism and hence leads to lesser loss of work time.
- Reduce health benefit costs
- Enhance morale
- Reduce risk of injury
- Improve job performance
- People who have a supportive supervisor, flexible and low job stress report greater work-life balance.

5. GREAT PLACE TO WORK INSTITUTE: THE VALUE OF CREATING GREAT WORKPLACES

Relationships at work matter, and in particular, the centrality of these three relationships influenced people's loyalty, commitment, and willingness to contribute to organizational goals and priorities. If leaders implemented practices and created programs and policies that contributed to these three The Great Place to Work Institute, has been studying great workplaces since its inception in 1991. In Robert Levering's 1988 book, *A Great Place to Work: What Makes Some Employers So Good — And Most So Bad*, he discussed great workplaces in terms of relationships and put forth the definition of a Great Place to Work that opened this book's chapter and that appears throughout the book. Specifically, he identified the relationships between employees and their leaders, between employees and their jobs, and between employees and each other as the indicators of a great place to work.

relationships, employees had a great workplace experience. It mattered less what the programs, policies, and practices were, and more that they were done in a way that strengthened relationships.

The Great Place to Work Model (see Figure 1.1) was developed during this time by the Institute's founders, Robert Levering and Amy Lyman. The Model was later formalized and today has five dimensions: Credibility, Respect, and Fairness (which, put together, comprise Trust); Pride; and Camaraderie.

Figure 1: The Great Place to Work Model

The Institute surveys 2 million people and gathers data on the cultures of nearly 6,000 companies worldwide every year. They evaluate companies for list membership using consistent methodology, whether the company is 60 people or 6,000, located in Brazil or India.

In these evaluations, they assess two aspects of workplaces.

- The first aspect, weighted more heavily, is the employee experience. The Institute administers a survey called the Trust Index © to determine the consistency of trust, pride, and camaraderie in the workplace and to learn directly from employees what makes their workplace great.
- The second aspect we evaluate for our best companies lists are the programs, policies, and practices leaders put in place for their employees. Using their Culture Audit trained evaluators assess each organization, and care is taken to calibrate ratings across the hundreds of companies that apply each year. From the Culture Audits, the Institute gathers thousands of best practices that, like the survey's employee comments, breathe life into the concepts of trust, pride, and camaraderie. These practices include Boston Consulting Group's policy of giving seasoned veterans incentives to have lunch with new hires.

The Institute holds several annual conferences around the world that bring leaders from the recognized organizations together to share their stories.

6. THE THREE RELATIONSHIPS

Figure 2: The Three Relationships

In the best companies, leaders at all levels have a strong commitment to creating strong ties between the employee and the organization. Indeed, enhancing trust, pride, and camaraderie in the workplace is *the* central task of effective leadership in today's organization.

6.1 Trust

It is often said that employees tend to join organizations, but leave their managers. There are situations where individuals worked in the same area in the same department and they don't trust each other. It's no wonder productivity suffers so much; everyone is looking out for themselves because they don't really believe their coworkers are looking out for their best interest. Somehow the feeling is that an associate is somewhere trying to bring them down with a negative comment. The ideal place needs an environment that fosters trust and loyalty to the company and to each other. What if everyone consistently encouraged and motivated each other as well as share their best demonstrated practices with the team. Do away with so many closed door meetings.

Trust also supports enhanced cooperation. When we trust one another in our teams, we are more likely to encourage mutual growth, seek the win - win, and resolve conflicts more constructively. We are more willing to give extra to get the job done.

Employees described three qualities that are necessary to their experience of trust, and these three qualities are the first three dimensions of the Great Place to Work Model. The first, Credibility, involves the sense that leaders give employees appropriate information, are competent to lead the organization, and that their actions match their words. The second, Respect, refers to the employees' beliefs that leaders support them personally and professionally, that they wish to collaborate with them on suggestions and decisions, and that leaders care about them as people and not just as employees.

The final group of perceptions, Fairness, involves the belief that leaders create a level playing field, treating people equitably and impartially, and allowing them to voice concerns about decisions.

6.2 Pride

The second of the three relationships found in great workplaces (and the fourth dimension of the Great Place to Work Model) is the relationship between the individual and his or her work. Essentially, people experience a great workplace when they feel as though they make a difference in their organization, that their work is meaningful. They are also proud of their team's accomplishments, and the contributions the organization makes to the community at large. Often, pride comes from the employee's sense that he or she contributes to the

organization's values, the goods and services it produces, and the philanthropic contributions the organization makes to better their communities.

6.3 Camaraderie

Great workplaces foster healthy and strong relationships between people, and given this, the final dimension of the Great Place to Work Model is Camaraderie. At great workplaces, people feel welcomed from the very first day, through everything from formal orientation activities to meaningful interactions with co-workers and mentors. They feel as though everyone is working toward one common goal, and that they can be authentic at work. While some degree of camaraderie can be attributed to good hiring, organizations also take action to build a sense of family at work. They provide opportunities for employees to collaborate and interact outside of work. Some also provide outlets for employees to help one another in times of need.

7.TEN WAYS TO CREATE A POSITIVE WORK ENVIRONMENT

There are several things a leader/manager can do to make the work environment a positive one and to facilitate a feeling of cooperation, teamwork and joy among the staff. Some of these are:

7.1 Build Trust

Trust is about doing what you say you are going to do and being who you say you are. It's about showing your staff in everything you do, that you are reliable, responsible and accountable, and that they can rely on you for consistency. When your words and behaviour are congruent you foster trust. If they see that you are consistent you will build trust, but if they see your words don't match your behaviours their trust in you will be destroyed. Even when dealing with uncomfortable situations, if you are honest and up front it will make things easier for everyone. Even if they don't like what you are saying, if you say it honestly, compassionately and tactfully they will respect and trust you. Your employees' level of trust will also be determined by how well you keep confidences and don't disclose discussions that have been held in private. They have to know they can talk with you about sensitive subjects and that the information they share with you will be kept in strict confidence. Confidentiality also applies to never discussing one employee with another, except in positive terms. A good manager never talks negatively about his/her team.

7.2 Communicate positively and openly

In order to create a positive work environment each employee needs to feel valued. This is best accomplished through your listening to each person and honouring each one for what s/he has to say. One important aspect of communicating openly is to meet with your staff and discuss your organization's philosophy, values, mission and goals. Ask for their ideas and thoughts on how they individually and as a team can help your unit to exemplify these. Then lead a discussion on the ways they all see these being fulfilled within your work group. After your staff has shared their ideas, take time to share your own vision of how you see everyone working together as a circle in which everyone is equal and on the same level, rather than a pyramid where supervisors and administrators are at the top, and the staff is at the bottom. Also share your work ethics, commitment to the job and facility, and your values. Talking about and modelling your own work ethic will set an example of what your expectations are for your staff.

7.3 Expect the best from your staff

There is a concept called 'The Self-Fulfilling Prophecy' which states that people generally will perform in the way others expect them to perform. So, if you have high expectations for your staff, treat them as if they are capable, competent people and expect them to function as such, they will rise to the occasion and be the excellent employees you see them to be. However, if you expect them to be mediocre and treat them as if they can't function well on their own, that is the behaviour they will give you. A good supervisor always has high expectations for his/her staff and treats them accordingly.

7.4 Create Team Spirit

One of our basic human needs is to feel we belong to something bigger than ourselves, and for many people that need is met by being part of a supportive work group. As a supervisor, part of your job is to create a feeling of

unity among your staff. This unity will help your team members feel valued and that they belong. As a result they will want to be at work, tardiness and absenteeism will be minimal, your team will function smoothly and your unit will be better able to carry out the missions and goals of your organization.

To foster this team feeling you must convey to the entire staff that every person plays an important role. Encourage an attitude of cooperation rather than competition. When you create team spirit and identity, staff members will see themselves as a group of people all working for a common goal, rather than a bunch of individuals competing with each other.

One easy exercise is to begin staff meetings by going around the table and having each person say one nice thing about the person on their right or left.

There are many other ways a supervisor can foster team spirit. Some of these are:

- Give verbal and written communication to individuals and the group for jobs well done.
- Make sure team members know a bit about each other's personal life by setting aside 5 minutes at each staff meeting to have one person tell about something positive that's happened in their life in the past month.
- Let them know that you are also part of the team by asking your staff what they need from you to make their job more satisfactory, and doing your best to provide it.
- Ensure that humour is part of the daily work environment. Put a humour section on the bulletin board and invite team members to post things they find funny (keeping good taste in mind, of course). Also, encourage them to respectfully find the humour in situations at work. It's important for you as the supervisor to learn to laugh at yourself, and model this for your staff. Let them know that since we all are human we make mistakes. It's much better to find the lesson and humour in mistakes than to become upset over them.
- Do problem solving at staff meetings.

7.5 Give Recognition and Appreciation

Give recognition and appreciation to everyone at every opportunity. For example: "Mr.Sharma, thank you for staying overtime yesterday. I really appreciate your positive, can-do attitude." When verbalizing appreciation try to make it as personal as possible. Rather than just saying something vague like "good job", be specific about the personal quality or skill your team member brought to the task. Recognizing excellent job performance and attitude, and showing appreciation for these things will go a long way towards making your staff members feel that they are a valued and respected part of the team.

7.6 Give Credit and Take Responsibility

Always give credit for success to your staff, and take responsibility when things don't go well. As the boss it's your job to make sure your staff is well trained, capable and competent. If for some reason they fail to perform their job in the expected manner, it's your responsibility to insure that they receive further direction and training so they will perform up to standards.

7.7 Be Approachable

Always present an attitude of approachability to your staff and customers. Indicate by your manner that you are available and happy to speak with people from all levels and positions. Also, always be prepared to listen to whatever they want to share with you, and validate what you've heard. If they have concerns, tell them you will look into it and get back to them by a certain time. Then be sure you do! It's important that every day you go out and walk about your business in order to connect with people. Be sure that as you walk through the business you smile and make eye contact with everyone you pass. Act in a friendly manner, call people by name, be approachable, and show interest in what's going on. Also, have an open door policy, where anyone at any level is welcome to come talk with you if they feel the need. When they do come talk with you, be aware of your body language. Come around to the front of your desk and sit facing them while you talk so that there is no physical barrier between you.

7.8 Provide a Positive Physical Environment

Ensure that the physical environment on your workplace is clean, bright, attractive and cheerful. Make sure it has as much natural light as possible, and that each staff member has room for their own personal space. Physical factors in the workplace such as poor layout or overcrowding can lead to common types of accident such as tripping or striking against objects. Make your workspace look attractive to you. Try new furniture, photos, posters, mirrors, flowers, knick knacks, statues, rugs, artwork, crystals, etc.

7.9 Make Staff Evaluations a Positive Experience

Staff evaluation is a great opportunity for you to praise your employees for their cooperative spirit and all their efforts in doing an excellent job. Even if you need to discuss some areas in which the employee may need improvement, you can still make it a positive meeting by focusing on the good and all that they are doing right. Ensure that the staff evaluation is two-way. It's an opportunity for the employee to rate him/herself and also to rate you and your business. It's also the time to mutually create their career goals. Prior to the meeting, ask the employee to write out their evaluation of how they think they are doing in their job. Also ask them to write how they view you as a supervisor, and how they feel about working in your business. You will fill out the organization's standard evaluation form and write your thoughts on the employee's performance. Once you are in the meeting, ask the employee to share what they have written, and then discuss it with them. Then share your thoughts and what you have written. Some things to cover are:

- What skills would you like to develop in the next six months?
- What new knowledge would you like to gain in the next six months?
- What would you like to do differently with your peers?
- What can I do to assist you in the process of your development?

One of the most difficult aspects of a manager's job is counselling an employee who is not performing up to standards.

At the end of the evaluation process your staff member needs to be able to leave the meeting feeling that he/she has some control and personal power over their work life. This is a basic human need, and it's your job to support them by focusing on their strengths rather than their weaknesses. This doesn't mean you don't address their areas for growth, it just means that you focus on your belief in their ability to perform according to the needs of your business.

7.10 Make it fun

Everyone wants to be where people are having fun, so make your workplace feel happy and festive. Find reasons to celebrate together, such as birthdays, birth of a baby or grandchild, moving into a new house, etc., and having small parties to celebrate these events. If possible provide a cake, and put up a sign or banner in the break room saying "Today We Are Celebrating....." Ask your employees what would be fun for them and then implement what is feasible. There should be contests, games, social activities, for employees.

8. WHAT IS A FLEXIBLE WORKPLACE?

A flexible workplace supports employees to balance work and life commitments. It is an environment in which the workplace culture views this balance as positive and encourages employees to take advantage of options such as:

- Flexibility – allowing employees to have some capacity to adapt their workday to respond to family issues such as a child becoming ill or one who has special needs, school visits and parent-teacher interviews or special needs of elders. It typically includes family responsibility leave for employees.
- Supportive supervisors/managers whose management style values staff and is characterized by a desire to help employees achieve better balance between work and the rest of their lives.
- A culture that is family friendly - overall attitudes, beliefs, values that support work-family issues as legitimate workplace concerns, and as an opportunity to develop 'new ways of working'. Options include maternity, paternity, family and personal leave provisions.
- Alternative work arrangements – options are available to employees including daily or scheduled flex time arrangements, job-sharing, reduced hours, compressed work week, family leave options, part-time work, gradual retirement, telecommuting, other leaves and sabbatical options. Such alternative work

arrangements are seen as ways of working, and employees using them are not sidelined, marginalized or belittled.

- Recognition of child and elder care issues including support for child care, providing access to a service regarding child or elder care, establishing on-site child care or, developing a consortium with other employers in order to provide emergency child care. This includes accommodating the needs of employees who are breastfeeding their children.
- Use a broad definition of health: Good mental and physical health means more than the absence of illness, injury, and disease. It also means leading a balanced life, developing one’s potential, making a meaningful contribution to the organization, and having a say in workplace decisions.
- Link to strategic goals: Integrate health and well-being objectives into the organization’s business planning process, so that over time, all management decisions take health into account.

9. FORTUNE 100 BEST COMPANIES TO WORK FOR 2017

Every year Fortune ties up with Great Place to Work to list the 100 best companies to work for. This is done through an extensive employee survey that takes feedback from more than 232,000 employees at Great Place to Work–Certified™ companies with more than 1,000 employees. Two measures, namely Trust Index© survey and Culture Audit© questionnaire are used to rank the companies. The top 20 companies to work for are listed as under:

1. Google Inc.
2. Wegmans Food Markets, Inc.
3. The Boston Consulting Group, Inc
4. Baird
5. Edward Jones
6. Genentech
7. Ultimate Software
8. Salesforce
9. Acuity Insurance
10. Quicken Loans
11. Kimley-Horn
12. KPMG LLP
13. Intuit Inc.
14. Kimpton Hotels and Restaurants
15. SAS Institute Inc.
16. Burns & McDonnell
17. Capital One Financial Corporation
18. Workday, Inc.
19. Stryker Corporation
20. CHG Healthcare Services, Inc.

10. CASE STUDY- SAS: Taking Care of Their Greatest Asset

Fast Facts:

- Software developer
- Based in Cary, NC
- Founded in 1976
- Privately held
- 5,566 employees in the United States; 11,055 in offices around the world
- List - maker since 1998;
- Recognized internationally forty-eight times.

SAS is widely recognized as a great workplace. In fact, SAS is often cited as an inspiration by many of today's list - makers for their own facilities, wellness programs, and benefits. Even today, more than 34 years since its founding, SAS's list of benefits for employees is jaw - dropping. Some of the most unique include.

1. An on - site Health Care Centre with a 56 - member staff. There is no cost to employees or their covered dependents.
2. A SAS paediatrics health care provider is available by phone during the evening, weekend, and holiday hours for breastfeeding mothers and parents of young infants with questions and concerns.
3. An on - site childcare facility at headquarters for over 600 children, affiliated with the American Montessori Society. All full – time employees with one year of service are eligible to apply for placement, and when there is a waiting list, acceptance is based on length of time with the company, not on an employee ' s position in the organization. Parents at regional offices receive a childcare subsidy that is comparable to the on - site benefit.
4. Eldercare resources such as supportive networking opportunities; consultants; professional guidance for advance care directives; and a Caring Closet stocked with wheelchairs, crutches, shower seats, and more.
5. A 66,000- square- foot recreation and fitness facility with a class schedule similar to those found at community gyms. SAS goes the extra mile, though, and also offers specialty classes such as an intramural swim league, a modern dance class, and an indoor rowing crew.
6. Wellness and health classes and programs such as an Eco – family Challenge (where families record and earn points for earth - friendly activities), Teen Culinary Camp, sailing lessons, skateboard instruction, daddy-daughter dances, spring gardening workshops, and more.

SAS set out to be the most creative and innovative software developer around. Jennifer Mann, Vice President of Human Resources, puts it this way:

“Creativity is especially important to SAS because software is a product of the mind. Creativity doesn't come on demand. We're all inspired at different times. At SAS, we create a stimulating and flexible work environment, which allows employees to work when they are most innovative and productive. We trust them to do their jobs. From day one, SAS has taken a very organic approach to developing its benefits and programs. We focus on the employee.”

Dr. Jim Goodnight, founder of SAS and a software developer himself, is said to have wanted to create a place he would like to come to work every day.

SAS enjoys a 4 percent turnover rate, as compared to a 20 percent turnover rate in its industry. Estimates by Professor Jeffrey Pfeffer of Stanford University indicate that the company saves between \$ 75 – 100 million annually — a figure that drops right to the bottom line. Further, stable project teams support overall efficiency, quality, and long – term customer relationships. Most importantly, employees feel cared for as people. Dr. Goodnight's overarching philosophy is that “if you treat employees as if they make a difference to the company, they will make a difference to the company.”

11. Conclusion of the Study

To keep employees satisfied today, it takes an entirely different approach than it did just a few years ago. Indeed, one-third of the executives surveyed by Robert Half International Inc. have changed their opinions and now say the work environment is the most critical factor in keeping an employee satisfied in today's business world. In 1993, only 9% said that the work environment was an important factor in keeping employees satisfied.

Other critical factors include the importance of praise and recognition, and compensation each cited by 28% of those surveyed. Other significant changes include concern over promotions. Only 4% of executives say that promotions are a big factor in keeping employees satisfied today, compared with 26% who said that in 1993. A great workplace is one where people trust the people they work for, take pride in what they do, and enjoy the people they work with.

There are several things a manager can do to make the work environment a positive one, namely, build trust, communicate positively and openly, expect the best from your staff, create team spirit, give recognition and appreciation, give credit and take responsibility, be approachable, provide a positive physical environment, make

staff evaluations a positive experience and make it fun. The paper concludes with a case study of SAS Institute Inc., which was ranked among the top 20 companies in Fortune 100 Best Companies to Work for 2017. This study has important implications for companies as it motivates them to create a healthy positive work environment in order to get the best results from their employees.

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